

ABOUT SOME TEACHING METHODS OF LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Abstract: *The article deals with the problems of teaching English through directions related to a specific field.*

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Language is the main means of communication, without which it is difficult to imagine the existence and development of human society. Today, at a time when there are great changes in social relations in our world, communication media (information technologies) require the improvement of students' communicative skills, they can exchange ideas in different situations during interaction with other participants of communication, language and so It is necessary to use the norms of behavior correctly. In such conditions, the main purpose of a foreign language is the formation of communicative skills, that is, it is required to carry out interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language. In the 21st century, the processes of globalization and integration have affected all aspects of human activity, and the need for professionally oriented communication has begun a new era. The modern, ever-changing reality makes high demands on specialists, who must not only have professional skills and abilities but also be highly qualified in the field of language communication. Language, as the main means of communication, acts as a kind of window reflecting the changes taking place in society.

The need for a scientific approach to the analysis of linguistic features of various types of texts and registers was noted by many authors in the 60s. Although their research was limited to the concept of "register" and was conducted at the word and sentence level, reliable corpus-based statistics were obtained on the prevalence of different types of words and structures in texts belonging to different registers. With the development of computer technology, corpus linguistics has become widespread. Research shows that the analysis of text corpus in the preparation of educational programs provides reliable statistical information about the structure and linguistic

properties of texts of various genres, a lot of real examples, allows to combine the study of different fields of knowledge. Although there is no unified whole within the multidisciplinary approach that is relevant to the programs of modern higher education institutions, it can unite around the overall goal and process of teaching English for special purposes.

Based on innovative approaches in developed countries of the world aimed at developing students' information-communicative competence improvement of the modernization didactic system, metacompetencies effective rapid learning of foreign languages by students on the basis of formation conducting a number of scientific researches on the development of forms, methods and tools is going Socio-economic, which is rapidly changing today phenomena, in particular, in the institutions of the continuous education system in the conditions of the pandemic to understand the theoretical foundations of teaching foreign languages in the form of mixed education, taking into account the critical-analytical thinking qualities of learners learning a foreign language independently, whole education based on a cluster approach to ensure optimal integration of traditional and online education in the system mechanism, professional in future teachers in the conditions of digital educational environment improving the didactic-methodical system of competence formation requires. In the process of learning, the correct formation of lexical, grammatical, and pronunciation concepts, the correct composition of the knowledge system, and self-control skills in the student's mind are components of innovative pedagogical technologies. Currently, the most effective teaching methods in the educational process, which are guaranteed to achieve the goals set by teachers and pedagogues, form the basis for students to think independently, make independent decisions, solve their problems, and get out of various situations without difficulty. such teaching methods capable of being prepared are the most advanced features of pedagogical technology.

Today, with the initiatives of our president, great attention is being paid to language learning in our country. If we look at the above, we will once again be convinced of how important language is in the development of our country. Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming one of the integral parts of professional education. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists in various fields, their demand for language learning is high. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education. People learn such knowledge first at school, college, lyceum, and then at

institutes, training courses, or independently by getting acquainted with the basic information sets that help to learn a foreign language. Today, there are large collections of educational materials for people with different levels of language skills. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and skills of teachers. The ability to use information technologies and modern teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher can solve specific educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, the ability to choose the most effective methods to achieve one's goals is formed. The use of several methods of teaching and learning will give effective results. Teaching is carried out in small steps and is based on the student's existing knowledge system. As time progresses, innovations in every field are increasing. Different styles are also emerging in language teaching. A step-by-step approach to teaching English based on the learner's potential, level, and age gives good results. In this case, students are divided into groups based on teaching at the primary level, teaching at the middle level, and teaching at the higher level. A special program is developed by the teacher for each stage.

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